

PYRONE AND RELATED COMPOUNDS. PART III. ACTION OF BASES ON 2:6-DIHYDROXYPYRONE

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The reaction of aniline, ammonium acetate, pyridine and piperidine on dihydroxypyrrone has been studied. Aniline brings about the fission of the pyrone ring and forms an anilic acid, a dianilide and in conjunction with zinc chloride forms *N*-phenyl-2:6-dihydroxypyridone. Ammonium acetate, pyridine and piperidine form oxonium compounds with the ring-oxygen. The basicity of the ring oxygen is discussed.

The pyrones (I) in general by the action of ammonia are converted into the corresponding pyridones (II) or the oxypyridines (III).

Dihydroxypyrrone (I, $R=R'=OH$) does not give any isolable product by the action of ammonia but with alcoholic ammonia it gives the diammonium compound of 2:6-dihydroxypyridone (II, $R=R'=OH$, $2NH_3$, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 138).

By the action of aniline on pyrone (I, $R=R'=H$) in dilute acetic acid Borsche and Bonacker (*Ber.*, 1921, 54B, 2678) obtained dioxymethylene acetone dianilide (IV, $R=R'=H$) obviously by the rupture of the pyrone ring.

The dianilo-ketone is converted by hydrochloric acid, sodium ethylate or by distillation in vacuum into *N*-phenylpyridone (V, $R=R'=H$) (Smernoff, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1921, 4, 599).

The action of aniline on 2:6-dihydroxy-4-pyrone is, therefore, expected to give some interesting results and to throw some light on the structures of *N*-substituted-4 pyridones.

The dihydroxypyrrone gives with aniline in chloroform solution, a crystalline monobasic acid of the composition $C_{11}H_{11}O_4N$, m.p. 120° . This must have been formed by the fission caused by the addition of the molecule of aniline and must be anilic acid of the structure (VII).

When, however, the dihydroxypyrrone is boiled with excess of aniline and the excess removed with hydrochloric acid, another product of the composition $C_{17}H_{16}O_2N_2$, m.p. 157° , is obtained.

This is formed according to the equation, $C_6H_4O_2 + 2C_6H_5NH_2 = C_{17}H_{16}O_2N_2 + H_2O$ and therefore is the dianilide of acetone dicarboxylic acid (IV, $R=R'=OH$ or its keto form). The acetone dicarboxylic dianilide has been prepared by Besthorn and Garben (*Ber.*, 1900, 33, 3443) from acetone dicarboxylic ester and aniline at 100° .

But aniline in conjunction with fused zinc chloride reacts with dihydroxypyrrone in molecular proportions to give a third substance, m.p. 252° , of the composition $C_{11}H_9O_2N$. This third substance colours aqueous ferric chloride reddish violet on standing and is, therefore, 2:6-dihydroxy-1 phenyl-4 pyridone (V, $R=R'=OH$).

It forms a nitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 184° , and reacts with acetic anhydride and sulphuric acid to give a product $C_{12}H_{13}O_2N$, which is the diacetate (V, $R=R'=O'CO'CH_3$). According to Smernoff the pyridone should have the structure (VI, $R=R'=OH$) which is not likely in view of the fact that the substance forms a nitrophenylhydrazone (*cf.* Bedekar, Kaushal and Deshpande, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 466).

The dihydroxypyrrone and ammonium acetate at 0° yield an amorphous light white solid, m.p. 210° . Probably the ammonium acetate has converted the dihydroxypyrrone into the corresponding pyridone (II, $R=R'=OH$). On referring to the literature it was found that 2:6-dihydroxypyrrone, which can also be regarded as trihydroxypyridine or triketopiperidine, is a yellowish sandy powder, m.p. $200-230^\circ$, and it is very soluble in hot water and forms a mono-oxime, m.p. 196° (*Ber.*, 1887, 20, 2655).

The compound melting at 210° forms an oxime, m.p. 180° , and forms an acetate, m.p. 160° , which strikingly does not contain any nitrogen. All these compounds colour aqueous ferric chloride.

It, therefore, follows that ammonium acetate as expected has not been able to replace the oxygen of the ring by the-NH group. The analysis of the compound, melting at 210° , shows that it is only the ammonia addition product of the dihydroxypyrrone (VIII, $X=NH_3$), in which the oxygen is quadrivalent and nitrogen pentavalent. On heating alone it evolves ammonia.

The analysis of the oxime agrees with $C_6H_7O_2N$ and is, therefore, the oxime of the dihydroxypyrrone (IX) formed as shown above.

The analysis of the acetate melting at 160° corresponds to the formula $C_8H_8O_4$ and, therefore, is the diacetate of the dihydroxypyrrone (I, $R=R'=O'CO'CH_3$). This is confirmed by an independent observation that the disodium compound of the dihydroxypyrrone, when heated with acetyl chloride, gives the same product.

This is not quite impossible in view of the fact that the pyrrone structure (I, $R=R'=OH$) is expected to impart to the compound basic properties, while the group $-C(OH):CH-$, is expected to impart to the compound acidic properties. It has been shown by the author (*loc. cit.*) that the compound does not form oxonium salts with hydrochloric acid, chloroplatinic acid or picric acid. This is due to the presence of the negative -OH groups in the 2:6 positions, the oxygen behaves as though it were acidic and actually forms oxonium compound with bases like ammonia. This is further confirmed by the reaction of the dihydroxypyrrone with pyridine or piperidine.

On mixing the dihydroxypyrrone and pyridine, heat is evolved and a gummy solid separates which on purifying melts at 152° , and has the composition $C_{10}H_8O_2N$. This must have been formed by the addition of one molecule of pyridine to one of the dihydroxypyrrone.

On gentle heating the compound $C_{10}H_7O_2N$ evolves pyridine and is, therefore, the oxonium compound (VIII, $X=NC_2H_5$). Similarly piperidine forms the oxonium compound (VIII, $X=NC_2H_{11}$). Like the former it evolves piperidine on gentle warming and colours aqueous ferric chloride violet.

Thus the basic function of the ring oxygen in 4-pyrones is dependent on the nature of the groups in the 2 : 6-positions. If R and R' are positive organic radicals, the ring oxygen becomes strongly basic, e.g. pyrone (I, $R=R'=H$), dimethylpyrone (I, $R=R'=CH_3$) or diethylpyrone (I, $R=R'=C_2H_5$) are known to form well defined oxonium salts with acids (cf. Willstätter and Dummerer, *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 3740; Collie and Tickle, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 78, 710; Deshapande *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 305). Here H, CH_3 or C_2H_5 are positive organic radicals. But when R and R' are negative, the basic function of the ring oxygen is marred. For instance chelidonic acid or the ester (I, $R=R'=COOH$ or $COOEt$) are not known to form any oxonium salts with acids. In the case of the dihydroxypyrene the basic function of the ring oxygen is decreased to such an extent that it actually forms oxonium compounds with bases.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the Anilic Acid (VII).—The reaction between aniline and the dihydroxypyrene takes place with or without the use of the solvent. Equimolecular quantities of the reactants were separately dissolved in chloroform and the solutions were mixed at the ordinary temperature. A slight evolution of heat was observed. On evaporating the solvent at the room temperature a viscous mass was left which on rubbing gradually solidified. This was put on a porous tile and the solid freed from the gum by rubbing with ether and hydrochloric acid. The anilic acid was crystallised from dilute alcohol as soft needles, m.p. $120-21^\circ$. (Found : C, 59.6; H, 4.9; N, 6.3. $C_{11}H_{11}O_4N$ requires C, 59.9; H, 4.9; N, 6.3 per cent).

Preparation of the Dianilide (IV, $R=R'=OH$).—The dihydroxypyrene (2 g.) was mixed with aniline (5 c.c.). After the initial reaction subsided, the mixture was boiled for 10 minutes when a portion on rubbing with hydrochloric acid gave a solid. It was then left in contact with hydrochloric acid to free it from aniline. The solid separating was well rubbed, filtered and washed with alcohol. It was then dried on a porous tile; yield of the crude product 1 g. It crystallised from alcohol as thick small yellow needles, m.p. 157° . (Found : N, 9.0. $C_{11}H_{11}O_4N_2$ requires N, 9.4 per cent).

2 : 6-Dihydroxy-N-phenyl-4-pyridone (V, $R=R'=OH$).—(On addition of 1.5 g. of aniline (1 mol.) to 2 g. of dihydroxypyrene (1 mol.) a little frothing took place and heat was evolved. It was cooled and after addition of fused zinc chloride (5 g.) was refluxed for 10-15 minutes till the zinc chloride had gone into solution. On cooling and rubbing a solid separated which was filtered, washed and dried, yield 1 g. It was crystallised from absolute alcohol when it came out as almost colourless thick clusters of needles, m.p. 252° (darkening at 230°). (Found : N, 6.4. $C_{11}H_{11}O_4N$ requires N, 6.8 per cent).

The *nitrophenylhydrazone* was prepared by warming in hot water for 15 minutes equivalent quantities of the reacting substances in glacial acetic acid solution and diluting with water. On crystallisation from alcohol it came out as reddish brown prisms or globules, m.p. $184-85^\circ$.

The *diacetate* (V, $R=R'=O\cdot CO\cdot CH_3$) was prepared in the usual manner with acetic anhydride and traces of sulphuric acid. It was crystallised from alcohol and charcoal as long thin needles having a very pale yellow colour, m.p. 190° . (Found : C, 62.4; H, 4.2. $C_{11}H_{11}O_6N$ requires C, 62.7; H, 4.5 per cent).

Action of Ammonium Acetate on 2 : 6-Dihydroxypyrrone : Formation of the Oxonium Compound (VIII, X=NH₂).—Ammonium acetate (10 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (20 c.c.) and the dihydroxypyrrone (4 g.) was gradually added to it under ice-cooling. The reaction started almost immediately for the dihydroxypyrrone began to disappear and a white solid appeared in its place. This was left in an ice-chest for 24 hours and then filtered and washed with alcohol. Dried on a porous plate it melted at 200°, yield 3 g. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol from which it separated as clusters of small needles, m.p. 210° changing to a red liquid. (Found : N, 8·7. C₈H₇O₄N, H₂O requires N, 8·6 per cent).

The substance gives a beautiful violet colour to ferric chloride and evolves ammonia simply on heating.

Formation of the Oxime (IX).—To the hot aqueous solution of the compound (VIII, X=NH₂), on adding hydroxylamine hydrochloride solution a crystalline soft precipitate separated or it was obtained by boiling the solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride and the compound (VIII, X=NH₂). This was crystallised from 90% alcohol as small microscopical prisms, m.p. 180° (decomp.). (Found : N, 9·6. C₈H₉O₂N requires N, 9·5 per cent).

The oxime gives a violet colour to ferric chloride which deepens on standing.

Formation of the Acetate (I, R=R'=OCOCH₃).—To the compound (VIII, X=NH₂) acetic anhydride was added in excess and two drops of sulphuric acid. The mixture was heated for 5 minutes and poured on ice when after about 5 minutes the acetate separated as small crystalline shining plates having a very faint pinkish tinge, m.p. 160° to a red liquid. (Found : C, 50·3 ; H, 3·6. C₁₀H₉O₆ requires C, 50·9 ; H, 3·8 per cent)

This also gives a reddish violet colour to ferric chloride but only after standing for sometime.

On boiling the disodium dihydroxypyrrone with excess of acetyl chloride in presence of a trace of sulphuric acid and pouring into water the same diacetate separated as a light pinkish solid, m.p. 159-60°.

Reaction of Dihydroxypyrrone and Pyridine : The Oxonium Compound (VIII, X=NC₅H₅).—To well cooled pyridine was added the dihydroxypyrrone when heat was evolved and a slight decomposition took place with evolution of carbon dioxide. On standing and rubbing the mass turned into a yellowish brown paste which was pressed on a porous tile. The resulting solid was crystallised from 80% alcohol as light needles, m.p. 152°. (Found : N, 6·8. C₁₄H₉O₄N requires N, 6·8 per cent).

On gentle heating the compound darkened and evolved pyridine. It dissolves in water, the solution being slightly acid to litmus. It colours a aqueous ferric chloride violet.

Reaction of Dihydroxypyrrone and Piperidine : The Oxonium Compound (VIII, X=NC₅H₁₁).—To well cooled piperidine, the dihydroxypyrrone was added in slight excess and the mixture stirred well when gradually the pyrrone went into solution and a thick jelly-like mass was formed. On rubbing it with benzene it became granular. It was filtered and pressed on a porous tile. Purified by washing it melted at 139°. It could be crystallised from benzene as small microscopical prisms having a very pale yellow colour, m.p. 139-40°. (Found : N, 6·4. C₁₆H₁₅O₄N requires N, 6·6 per cent).

The substance is very soluble in water and evolves piperidine on gentle warming or heating. With aqueous ferric chloride it develops a beautiful violet colour at once.

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